

Studies on the Hydroxo Cyanogen Compounds: I. A Spectrophotometric Study of the Complex Formation of Vanadium (IV) with Potassium Aquo Hydroxocyanomolybdate (IV)

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The composition and stability of vanadium (IV)-tripotassium aquo trihydroxy-tetracyanomolybdate (IV) complex has been studied by spectrophotometric measurements. The violet coloured complex ($\lambda_{\max}$ 550 m μ at pH 6.0) have a 1:1 (metal: ligand) composition. The optimum pH range is from 5.25 to 7.5. The apparent stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at 25° were evaluated as $(7.2 \pm 0.1) 10^4$ and (-6.66 ± 0.01) Kcals., respectively.

A few insoluble metal complexes of hydroxocyanomolybdates^{1,2} have been studied by the method of chemical analysis, but no systematic work has been done. The present communication deals with our studies on some aspects of vanadium (IV)—tripotassium aquo trihydroxytetracyanomolybdate (IV) interaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of tripotassium aquo trihydroxytetracyanomolybdate(IV) dihydrate: Tripotassium aquo trihydroxytetracyanomolybdate (IV) dihydrate was prepared as follows: First of all the insoluble red complex $K_4 [Mo(OH)_4 (CN)_4]$ was prepared by the method of Jakob and Jakob². It was then hydrolysed in double distilled water to give the soluble blue complex $K_3 [Mo^{IV} (OH)_3 (CN)_4, H_2O]^3$, which was then isolated from the solution by fractional precipitation with ethanol. The product was dried over $CaCl_2$ in vacuum desiccator and analysed. Anal. Calcd. for $K_3 [Mo(OH)_3(CN)_4, H_2O], 2H_2O$: Mo, 22.69; K, 27.77; C, 11.37; N, 13.26; H, 2.147; O, 22.72. Found: Mo, 24.1; K, 28.1; C, 11.99; N, 13.03; H, 2.06; O (by difference), 20.72%.

Its solution was made in double distilled water and strength was determined oxidimetrically by titrating against $K_3 [Fe(CN)_6]^4$. The solution was stored in an amber coloured bottle wrapped with black paper.

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Vanadyl sulphate (a monohydrate of B.D.H.) was dissolved in air free double distilled water and its concentration was determined gravimetrically⁵. Fresh solution was always prepared just before use.

Absorbance measurements were carried out with Bausch and Lomb spectronic 20 colorimeter. The pH measurements of the solutions were recorded with Beckman pH-meter model H2 with glass and calomel electrodes.

The pH of the solutions was adjusted by the addition of ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer.

All measurements were carried out at 25°.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stability of the color: The intensity of the color developed increases with time and attains a maximum in about 15 minutes. Hence all the measurements were made half an hour after mixing the solutions.

Fig. 1: Absorption spectra of vanadium (IV)-hydroxocyanomolybdate.

Concentration of reactants = M/100, pH 6.0

VO_2SO_4 : Hydroxocyanomolybdate

A—O:	1	E—1:	1
B—1:	0	F—2:	1
C—1:	3	G—3:	1
D—1:	2		

Fig. 2: Job Curves. at 550 mμ, pH 6.0 Concentration of reactants: O-M/150; O-M/300; O-M/400.

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Fig. 3: Mole ratio curves at 550 m μ , pH 6.0
Concentration of reactants: O-M/150;
O-M/200; O-M/300.

Fig. 4: Mole ratio curves at 550 m μ , pH 6.0
Concentration of reactants: O-M/150;
O-M/200; OM/300.

The Nature of the Complex Formed: Vosburgh and Cooper's⁶ method was employed to determine the nature of the complex formed. Reactants were mixed in different stoichiometric ratios and absorbance of each mixture was measured at suitable wave lengths within the range of 365 to 650 m μ . The results, represented graphically in fig. 1, show that the maximum absorbance of the hydroxy cyanide is at 615 m μ ⁷ (curve A), whereas for curves C, D, E, F, and G, the region of maximum absorbance shifts to 550 m μ at pH 6.0. This indicates that only one complex, with $\lambda_{\max}$ at 550 m μ , is formed under the specified conditions.

Complex Formation: The composition of the complex was established by two methods, viz., the Job's continuous variation method⁸ (fig. 2) and mole ratio method⁹ (figs. 3 & 4).

As shown in figs. 2, 3 and 4, the results indicate that Vanadium (IV) forms a 1-to-1 complex with the reagent. Hence the formula of the complex may be designated as $KVO^{II}[Mo^{IV}(OH)_3(CN)_4(H_2O)]$.

Effect of pH: Several mixtures containing vanadyl sulphate and the reagent in the ratio of 1 : 1 were prepared, their pH's were adjusted to different values, and then their absorbance were measured at different wave lengths. The results show that $\lambda_{\max}$ of the complex (550m μ) holds good between pH 5.25 to 7.5; this is, therefore, the pH range over which the complex is stable.

The apparent stability constant was calculated by the method of Dey and Mukherjee¹⁰ using Job's curves with optical density as the ordinate and the composition of the mixture as abscissa. It comes out to be $(7.2 \pm 0.1) \times 10^4$.

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The free energy of formation of the complex was determined with the help of the expression :

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K,$$

where ΔF° is the standard free energy change, R, the gas constant and T, the absolute temperature. The free energy of formation of the complex works out to be (-6.6 ± 0.01) Kcals. at 25°.

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